

VISUAL CULTURE, HISTORY AND IMAGE: THE WAR AGAINST PARAGUAY

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ABSTRACT

The War against Paraguay (1864–1870), the largest armed conflict in 19th-century South America, extended beyond the battlefield into the media sphere, particularly through the illustrated Brazilian press. This study investigates the visual representations of the war produced by illustrators such as Henrique Fleiuss and Angelo Agostini. Their engravings, published in periodicals like *Semana Illustrada* and *A Vida Fluminense*, either reinforced patriotic ideals of the Empire or denounced the horrors of war. Through iconographic analysis, cross-referenced with historical, the *Quadros Históricos da Guerra do Paraguai* collection, and recent historiography, the research reveals how these images shaped public perceptions and contributed to symbolic documents disputes over the memory of the conflict. The 19th-century press thus became a site for the construction and contestation of meaning, where war was drawn, interpreted, and commodified for a visually eager readership.

Keywords: War against Paraguay; Illustrated press; Henrique Fleiuss; Angelo Agostini; Historical paintings.

INTRODUCTION

The war against Paraguay (1864–1870) remains one of the most impactful and controversial episodes in 19th-century South American history. Its consequences extended beyond the battlefield, reshaping not only geopolitical borders but also social structures, political practices, and mechanisms for constructing memory. In Brazil, in particular, this conflict consolidated a vigorous visual repertoire that, through illustrated periodicals, lithographs, and iconographic collections, was mobilized not only to inform the population but also to organize a visual narrative of the war that still reverberates today in the ways the episode is remembered and taught.

At the same time that the illustrated press gave a face to the ongoing conflict, the State and its civilian and military agents began to instrumentalize these images in strategies of

symbolic consecration and civic disciplining, transforming the perspective on the war into a field of dispute.

It is within this context that the present article is situated, whose central objective is to examine the visual representations of the war against Paraguay in the Brazilian illustrated press of the 19th century, focusing on the work of two of the most prominent graphic artists of the period, Henrique Fleiuss and Angelo Agostini, and on the analysis of the collection *Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War*, published in the 1870s.

More than focusing on the aesthetic content of the images, the aim is to understand how such visual representations functioned as devices for the symbolic construction of war, articulating discourses of power, identity, and memory. In other words, this study investigates how war was conceived, interpreted, appropriated, and contested not only on the battlefields, but also in the pages of newspapers and within the frames of lithographs that circulated among schools, public offices, libraries, and exhibition halls.

The hypothesis guiding this investigation¹ is that the visual art produced during and after the conflict constituted a political and moral pedagogy that actively contributed to the sedimentation of an official memory of the war. This visual art, forged in the tension between the artist's style and the interests of the State, materialized both in the press prints and in the lithographic compositions of the aforementioned collection, which were widely disseminated as school prizes, instructional materials, and diplomatic gifts.

By analyzing these images within the context of their production, circulation, and reception, the study seeks to demonstrate that they not only illustrated the conflict but also symbolically organized it, offering the public a specific way of seeing, feeling, receiving, and remembering the war.

In this sense, it is fundamental to consider that the production and circulation of these images occurred during a time of reconfiguration of public space in imperial Brazil. The expansion of the publishing market, the growth of the urban literate classes, and the emergence of a political culture based on visual communication favored the dissemination of illustrated periodicals such as *Semana Illustrada*, directed by Fleiuss, and *A Vida Fluminense*, where Agostini played a prominent role, in addition to *O Diabo Coxo* e *o Cabrião*, published between 1864 and 1867 in São Paulo.

¹This article is based on master's and doctoral research projects carried out between 2017 and 2023, respectively titled "*The lithographs of the collection Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War in the 1870s: Editorial Project and Images*" (Cunha, 2019) and "*The battles on the pages of newspapers: the War of the Triple Alliance and the editorial dispute between A Semana Ilustrada and A Vida Fluminense*" (Cunha, 2023), both funded by CAPES. Both are available in the Dissertations and Theses Repository of the Federal University of Juiz de Fora.

These periodicals, in turn, played an ambivalent role in the war: while reproducing heroic images of military feats and praising the commanders of the Army and Navy, they also disseminated satires, denunciations, and criticisms of the abuses and contradictions of the war effort. Thus, the illustrated press appears as an arena of disputes, in which multiple visual narratives were produced, disseminated, and negotiated before a readership increasingly sensitive to the languages of the image.

On the other hand, the collection *Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War*, published in the early 1870s, after the end of the conflict, presents a completely different editorial and political project, produced in a manner similar to what was observed in historical paintings of the time². Organized as a series of fascicles that combined lithographs based on paintings by renowned artists with laudatory texts of a patriotic nature, the collection was incorporated by the imperial State as an instrument for consecrating the memory of the war, being widely acquired by official bodies, as shown in various government reports³.

Purchased with public funds, distributed to civilian and military institutions, used as a school prize, and displayed in public spaces, this collection materialized the State's effort to establish a heroic and moralizing interpretation of the conflict, erasing its contradictions and violence. In this sense, it can be read as an exemplary artifact of what Pierre Bourdieu (1989) calls "symbolic violence": a form of imposing social meanings through seemingly neutral or consensual devices.

The analysis of these images therefore demands a perspective that goes beyond aesthetics. It is necessary to consider visibility as a political language, as a space for negotiating meanings, and as a field of ideological debate. In this respect, Art History and studies of visual culture offer fundamental tools for understanding the role of images in shaping sensibilities and collective memories.

As Georges Didi-Huberman (2010) proposes, every image is also a gesture of montage, of concealment and revelation; it is a field of forces in which the visible and the invisible intertwine. In the case of the war against Paraguay, it was also a way of defining the "self" and the "other." Thus, when we analyze the engravings from the periodicals used or the fascicles of

²This assertion becomes possible not only by analyzing the heroic iconography of the works, but also by considering the artists they represent: Pedro Américo, Victor Meirelles, and Eduardo De Martino, painters known for their historical paintings.

³This information is available in the *Revenue and Expenditure Statements of the Empire*, found in the Digital Newspaper Archive of the National Library. These documents cover part of the declared expenses of ministries and other agencies from 1875 to 1883.

the *Historical Pictures collection*, we are not only faced with representations of the war, but with visual acts that seek to organize the world, institute values, and fix memories.

From a methodological point of view, this article is based on three complementary pillars. The first is the iconographic analysis of the images, considering both their formal composition and their symbolic content and effects of meaning. The second is the study of the circulation and reception of these images, based on primary sources such as ministerial reports, the *Balance Sheets of Revenue and Expenditure of the Empire*, periodicals of the time, and records of the purchase and distribution of lithographic fascicles. The third is the articulation of these analyses with the historiography of the war against Paraguay and with studies on the press, memory, and visual culture. This approach allows us to understand images not as isolated objects, but as elements embedded in networks of production, circulation, and appropriation, marked by political interests, symbolic disputes, and specific institutional contexts.

With this framework, the article's structure is organized into six parts. After this introduction, the second chapter examines the trajectories of Angelo Agostini and Henrique Fleiuss in the illustrated press during the years of the conflict, highlighting their visual strategies, their political positions, and their contribution to the construction of the iconographic narratives of the war. Next, the third chapter analyzes in depth the collection * *Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War**, exploring its editorial project, its institutional circulation, and its effects on the establishment of a disciplined visual memory. The fourth chapter presents the central objectives of the research, followed by the fifth, which describes the methodology adopted. The sixth chapter discusses the concept of visual culture and its implications for the analysis of the images in question.

At the end of this journey, it is hoped to demonstrate that the war, although confined to the trenches of the 19th century, persists within the symbolic frameworks that surround it. And that these frameworks, often invisible, still condition our view of the past today, defining what we see, what we forget, and what we choose to remember.

ANGELO AGOSTINI AND HENRIQUE FLEIUSS IN THE ILLUSTRATED PRESS

During the war against Paraguay, the Brazilian illustrated press played a decisive role in the production and dissemination of images that served not only to inform, but also to interpret, criticize, and give meaning to the ongoing conflict. Two names stand out in this scenario for their unique graphic and editorial work: Henrique Fleiuss and Angelo Agostini. Their trajectories, although distinct in terms of visual strategies and political positions,

converge in the recognition of the image as a powerful language to intervene in public life, construct narratives, and influence sensibilities.

Henrique Fleiuss, with a solid artistic background and inspired by the traditions of European academic drawing, led one of the most important illustrated newspapers of imperial Brazil. *Semana Illustrada*, founded by him in 1860, operated as a hybrid vehicle, combining political satire, current events, arts, and science. In the midst of war, the periodical became a platform for glorifying the Brazilian military effort, highlighting the bravery of the troops, the victories on the battlefield, and the moral superiority of the Empire over the enemy.

His images often feature rigorous composition, with balanced framing, technical mastery of line, and a predominance of male figures in heroic poses. Soldiers on the march, generals with noble profiles, battle maps, and scenes of triumphs make up the iconographic repertoire that Fleiuss helped to crystallize as a visual hallmark of war.

At the same time, his work was not limited to an uncritically patriotic reading. Although most of his illustrations were aligned with official policy, there were moments when the artist incorporated elements of tension, such as the representation of wounded soldiers, the portrayal of material devastation, and the figure of the enemy stripped of military attire, brutalized, which demanded a visual positioning from the reader in the face of otherness. Such choices do not negate his legitimizing function for the Empire, but reveal that even seemingly neutral images carry ambivalences and critical potential, however subtle.

Angelo Agostini, of Italian origin and more self-taught, presents a bolder and more experimental graphic language, strongly influenced by the traditions of French graphic humor and the visual avant-garde of the 19th century. Since his work in *A Vida Fluminense*, Agostini has built a trajectory of challenging the imperial order, using caricature and visual chronicle as forms of direct intervention in political debate. However, this did not prevent him from covering the war and some of the feats of Brazilian soldiers, also presenting images of Paraguay, maps, and explanatory diagrams.

Regarding the war against Paraguay, his retrospective view was marked by irony, social criticism, and deconstruction of heroic narratives. His drawings do not always exalt the glory of combat, focusing more on revealing the human costs, the strategies of forced recruitment, the violence against civilian populations, and the discrepancies between the proclaimed values and the reality experienced in the trenches – characteristics more observed in his São Paulo phase.

In practical terms, Fleiuss operated within an aesthetic and political horizon of consolidating national identity, seeking to give symbolic cohesion to the imperial project.

Agostini, on the other hand, used the image more as an instrument of criticism and resistance, revealing the contradictions of the same project. The tension between these two perspectives offers the contemporary researcher a rich possibility for analysis, as it reveals the diversity of perspectives in dispute in the nineteenth-century press and the plurality of functions attributed to the image. More than mere illustrations, the engravings of both artists are configured as visual acts that produce meanings, mobilize affects, and influence discursive practices.

It is important to emphasize that both Fleiuss and Agostini worked in publishing environments that responded, albeit in different ways, to the demands of an expanding readership market. The growth of the literate population in cities, the advancement of transportation, the development of printing techniques, and the circulation of liberal and republican ideas formed the backdrop of a transforming literate culture, increasingly sensitive to graphic languages.

In this sense, the choice of themes, characters, and framing by the illustrators responded both to their personal convictions and to the expectations of the public and the strategies of the publishers. The images of war, therefore, were also products of a symbolic market in dispute, in which visibility was negotiated between aesthetic, political, and commercial interests.

It is interesting to point out here that the visual production of the time was largely based on oral accounts, journalistic texts, war correspondence, and other pre-existing representations from the *front*. Both characters relied on informants who lived through the war daily and sent, whenever possible, sketches, reports, and other information that gave rise to the engravings.

However, the artists' creativity was essential to translating such documents onto paper. In this mediation process, the artist's imagination played a central role, seeking to create a visibility that sounded plausible to viewers, but which was necessarily a translation. The war that the public saw in the newspapers was, therefore, a figurative war, assembled from fragments and organized according to diverse interests, even if based on accounts given by characters *in situ*.

The trajectories of Fleiuss and Agostini also reveal the intertwining of art and politics in the imperial context. Both maintained relationships with public figures, participated in state projects, and influenced the cultural debate of their time. Fleiuss, for example, had his Artistic Institute elevated to the title of Imperial, something that demonstrated his proximity to the monarchy and the importance observed in his business by Dom Pedro II. Agostini, although a fierce critic of the regime, circulated among republican, abolitionist, and liberal groups, frequently being the target of censorship or persecution, a reason that most likely led him to move from São Paulo. However, this scenario in Rio de Janeiro would change radically. In any

case, this insertion into the circuits of power and counter-power gives their images a historical density that transcends aesthetics and demands contextualized reading.

When comparing the works of Fleiuss and Agostini, it becomes evident that the illustrated press was not a homogeneous space for imperial propaganda, but rather a heterogeneous territory of symbolic dispute. Its pages housed both heroic narratives of the State and critiques of its practices; both idealized portrayals of the war and its biting caricatures. This ambivalence is one of the keys to understanding the role of visibility in the construction of the memory of the war against Paraguay. It shows that, before being established as a consensual episode in national history, the war was the stage for interpretative clashes in which the image functioned as a battlefield.

As authors such as Chartier (1990) and Burke (2004) point out, reading and viewing practices in the 19th century were permeated by cultural, social, and political filters that influenced the reception of images. The same drawing could be interpreted as an expression of patriotism or a denunciation of violence, depending on the reader's background, social position, and political engagement. In this sense, the images of Fleiuss and Agostini not only produced meanings but were also appropriated in distinct ways by their audiences. Understanding these appropriations is a fundamental task for any research that aims to investigate the circulation of images in the Brazilian Empire.

In short, the study of the trajectories of Henrique Fleiuss and Angelo Agostini in the illustrated press reveals that the war against Paraguay was shaped by multiple hands, by divergent perspectives, and by contrasting intentions. Their images offer historians not only a window into the past, but a dense field of meanings, tensions, and silences that help to understand how the visual memories of a conflict are forged.

Instead of simplifying the narrative of the war, these engravings pluralize it, highlighting that the struggle for representation was as important as the confrontations in the trenches. Fleiuss and Agostini, with their lines and inks, made the war a constantly contested visual territory, becoming essential sources for understanding the issues of the time.

The Collection: Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War

While the illustrated press constructed images of the war almost in real time, especially considering the limitations of transportation and communication at the time, following the advances and setbacks of the conflict, another front of representation was consolidating in the

post-war period: the production of official iconographies that sought to establish a glorious and disciplined memory of the military campaign.

"*Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War*" stands out, conceived as an editorial, artistic, and pedagogical project aimed at celebrating the Brazilian war effort through carefully produced, edited, and subsequently acquired and distributed images by the imperial state. Unlike the interpretative fluidity of caricatures and press engravings, these paintings proposed a stable, monumental, and monumentalizing visuality of the war, tailor-made for patriotic, civic, and school consumption, very close to the canons of historical painting.

Published in installments starting in the early 1870s, the collection comprised large-format lithographs based on historical paintings by renowned artists, accompanied by explanatory and laudatory texts. The images in the collection were created from paintings commissioned from artists such as Pedro Américo, Eduardo De Martino, and Victor Meirelles, whose academic training and institutional prestige ensured that the visual content aligned with the canons of European historical art.

The choice of foreign lithographs was not limited to a criterion of technical quality; it was also about conferring aesthetic legitimacy to the project, inserting the visuality of the Brazilian war within the mold of European academicism, demonstrating Brazilian "civility" to the rest of the world. This decision reaffirms the desire of the authors and also of the Empire itself to inscribe this visual narrative among the great modern epics, endowing it with prestige and permanence.

The scenes depicted in the *historical paintings* follow a logic of monumentalization that prioritizes episodes of victory, bravery, and heroic sacrifice. Among the themes represented, the passage of Humaitá, the siege of Curupaiti, and the surrender of the city of Uruguaiiana stand out, among others that demonstrate the advance and some of the successes of the Brazilian troops in Paraguay. The central characters are generally generals and officers in a haughty posture, soldiers in orderly formation. The violence of war is elided, aestheticized, and even softened: fallen bodies appear with nobility, blood is completely contained, and suffering is often converted into an expression of courage. All this, while the enemies are seen as inferior, brutalized, treated by the press of the time and by the collection itself as being the very embodiment of "barbarity."

This aesthetic of heroism is not merely visual. The texts accompanying the fascicles play a crucial role in organizing the reading of the images. Written in a laudatory tone, the verbal discourse explains, justifies, and frames what is seen, guiding the viewer to interpret the scenes as expressions of national virtue. Expressions such as "glory of the Army," "Brazilian

bravery," and "sacrifice for the Empire" are used in a vocabulary that does not admit ambivalence or criticism. The collection is, therefore, a complete symbolic apparatus: image and word articulated, though not always connected, to produce a controlled memory of the war, suitable to be disseminated as civic truth.

The circulation of this collection also deserves highlighting. Official documents from the time reveal that the imperial government acquired hundreds of copies of the work with public funds, using budgets from the Ministry of War and the Ministry of the Empire. These copies were distributed to public and private schools, libraries, municipal chambers, administrative offices, and military units. The objective was twofold: to reward academic merit with a work of aesthetic value and to instill in young people a patriotic consciousness aligned with official history. The iconography of war, therefore, was mobilized as a pedagogical tool, an instrument of symbolic discipline, and a reinforcement of imperial values. Not surprisingly, the paintings began to decorate the walls of classrooms, public offices, and government headquarters, giving war a prominent place in the collective imagination.

This institutional appropriation of the collection reveals a politics of memory that operated through visibility. In a context where written accounts had limited reach, and physical monuments were scarce, printed images became effective vehicles for fixing interpretations and consolidating consensus. The *Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War collection* thus functioned as a portable monument: a visual gallery of the national past that could be exhibited, browsed, given as a gift, and taught. Its portability and reproducibility broadened its reach and reinforced its memorial function.

The analysis of the collection's contents reveals, however, not only an effort at glorification, but also subtle mechanisms of erasure and silencing. The absence of representations of the Paraguayan enemy as a complex subject, the exclusion of scenes of sexual violence or civilian massacres, the disappearance of Black and Indigenous populations as direct participants in the war—all this denounces a selective visual policy aimed at constructing a homogeneous official memory. Even the figures of the volunteers for the fatherland, so exalted in oral discourses, appear in the background or as an indistinct mass, while the white, educated, and aristocratic officers are the main protagonists of the visual narrative.

In these paintings, the war is primarily a war of the elites. However, it is also the war of those unseen in the images, a crucial detail to consider when interpreting such representations.

Compared to the graphic production of Angelo Agostini or even the ambivalence of Henrique Fleiuss, the *Historical Pictures collection* represents the opposite pole of the visual dispute. While illustrated periodicals operated with the ephemerality of news and the freedom

of the authorial stroke, the lithographic fascicles sought to fix a perennial historical truth, resistant to criticism. The very physical support of the work—high-grammage paper, elaborate binding, large-format printing—reinforces its monumental vocation. These elements converge towards a broader political project: that of constructing a national iconography legitimizing the imperial order, in which the war against Paraguay occupies a foundational position.

It is thus possible to perceive that the collection "*Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War*" was not merely an artistic or editorial product, but a device used by the State, articulated with strategies for constructing official memory and consolidating the symbolic power of the Empire. As such, it needs to be understood in its complexity: as a historical document, as a pedagogical artifact, as an ideological instrument, and as an object of dispute. While aiming to pacify the past, it offered the present a visual narrative that excluded dissent and produced identity.

This operation of visually constructing the memory of war finds parallels in other historical contexts. One need only recall the iconographic campaigns promoted by Napoleon Bonaparte in France or the patriotic lithography in the United States after the Civil War. In all these cases, the State used images as a means of establishing an official history, aestheticizing violence, heroizing leaders, and erasing contradictions. Imperial Brazil was no exception. The *Historical Paintings* collection fits into this tradition of the political use of art, reaffirming the power of visibility in the struggle for social memories.

In summary, the analysis of the *Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War* collection reveals an articulated operation of symbolic production of the war as a national epic. Based on academically legitimized images, laudatory texts, and state distribution strategies, this collection constructed an authoritarian visual memory, centered on the heroism of the military elites and the silencing of marginalized experiences.

Unlike the multiple voices of the illustrated press, the *historical paintings of the Paraguayan War* offer a univocal narrative that still demands critical reading today. By investigating this iconographic collection, the present study seeks to highlight the mechanisms of selection, exclusion, and fixation of memory operated by the images, understanding them as political acts that shaped—and still shape—the way Brazil remembers its bloodiest war.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The investigation of visual representations of the war against Paraguay, as proposed here, is anchored in the conviction that images, far from being mere interpretative reflections

of reality, function as active mediators of historical experience, endowed with agency in the construction of meanings, affections, and collective memories. In this context, the objectives outlined for the research seek not only to map the iconographic production of the period, but also to understand the ways in which these images were produced, circulated, appropriated, and contested in different social, political, and institutional contexts.

This is therefore an investigation that lies at the intersection of art history, visual culture studies, the historiography of war, and the discursive practices of the nineteenth-century press.

The overall objective of this research is to critically analyze the visual representations of the war against Paraguay conveyed in the Brazilian illustrated press and in the collection "*Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War*," with a view to understanding how such images contributed to the construction of hegemonic narratives, symbolic disputes, and public memories about the conflict. This analysis stems from the recognition that the war was not limited to the realm of battles, but also unfolded as a communicational and imagistic phenomenon, in which different actors sought, through visual language, to shape the perception of the event and its meanings.

From this central axis, specific objectives are derived, which guide and organize the analytical path of the research:

1. To identify the main themes, characters, and iconographic frameworks present in the engravings of Henrique Fleiuss and Angelo Agostini about the war against Paraguay, considering their editorial insertions, political positions, and communication strategies with the reading public. This objective implies mapping the visual production of these artists within periodicals such as *Semana Illustrada* and *A Vida Fluminense*, understanding the role of the press as a mediator of war experiences and as a space of dispute over meanings.
2. This study analyzes the structure, content, and purposes of the collection "*Historical Pictures of the Paraguayan War*," addressing its aesthetic, pedagogical, and ideological dimensions. It aims to understand how this collection was conceived as a project for the official consecration of the war's memory, which episodes were selected to compose the visual narrative, and how the articulation between text and image operated as a device for symbolic normalization.
3. To investigate the processes of circulation and reception of war images in the context of imperial Brazil, with emphasis on forms of institutional distribution, school use, public exhibition, and appropriation by different social groups. This objective aims to trace the material and symbolic trajectories of the images, identifying the target

audiences, the means of dissemination, and the social effects of visibility in shaping historical memory.

4. Reflecting on the political uses of images in the 19th century, considering the iconographic production of war as part of a deliberate effort to construct identities, legitimize power, and organize the national past. This objective seeks to insert the Brazilian case into a broader discussion about the function of images in modernity, engaging with authors who consider the image as a form of discourse, domination, and resistance.
5. To contribute to the theoretical and methodological deepening of visual culture studies in Brazil, proposing an approach that combines iconographic and iconological analysis, reception studies, and critical reading of visual sources in conjunction with written texts, historiographical discourses, and official documents. The proposal is not only to interpret the content of the images, but to understand the regimes of visibility that make them possible, intelligible, and effective.

These objectives address gaps and challenges identified in recent historiography on the war against Paraguay. Despite the growing interest in the subject in recent decades—with studies ranging from the geopolitical aspects of the conflict to its social and economic consequences—there is still a relatively small number of studies that systematically deal with the visual representations produced in the heat of war and in its immediate post-conflict period.

When analyzed, these images are frequently used as supplementary illustrations, without due consideration of their codes, functions, and effects. By placing the images at the center of the analysis, this study proposes a methodological inversion that recognizes visibility as a privileged source for understanding the political culture and social memory of the 19th century.

Furthermore, the formulated objectives allow for an articulation between different scales of analysis: from the individual gesture of the artist to the editorial policy of newspapers, from the scene represented to the context of its circulation, from the image to the imaginary. This multi-scalar approach is fundamental to accounting for the complexity of the visual phenomenon, which involves both aesthetic decisions and institutional interests, cultural practices, and affective receptions. The image, in this sense, is understood as a point of convergence of multiple forces, and not as a simple mirror of reality.

Another important aspect is considering the agency of the illustrators, editors, and cultural mediators who worked in the production and dissemination of the images. Far from being passive agents of imperial power, figures like Fleiuss and Agostini played ambiguous

roles, sometimes collaborating in the construction of the official narrative, sometimes resisting it through satire, irony, and visual criticism. By analyzing their works with attention to their formal, thematic, and compositional choices, the aim is to understand how these artists negotiated their positions within a symbolic field marked by tensions, interests, and disputes.

At the same time, the research objectives are permeated by a concern with the processes of silencing and erasure operated by images. As studies by historians and critics of visibility demonstrate, every image produces visibility while simultaneously concealing elements of reality. In the case of the war against Paraguay, this is expressed, for example, in the scarcity of representations of women, Black people, and Indigenous people as active historical subjects; in the aestheticization of violence and death; in the suppression of scenes of civil devastation; and in the erasure of the contradictions of the war effort. Mapping these absences is as important as interpreting what was represented, because they reveal the boundaries of the visible and the limits of the narratable within a given regime of visibility.

Finally, the objectives outlined here respond to an ethical and political perspective on historiographical practice. By investigating how war was represented, remembered, and taught through images, the research also aims to reflect on the contemporary uses of this iconography, its impacts on historical education, and its implications for the construction of a more plural, critical, and inclusive memory.

In a context where disputes over historical narratives continue to mobilize emotions and politics, revisiting images of the war against Paraguay is also an act of intellectual responsibility, seeking to deconstruct foundational myths and illuminate the layers of meaning that make up the nation's visual past.

METHODOLOGY USED

This research falls within the field of Art History and Visual Culture, operating on the understanding that images are complete historical documents, capable of expressing power relations, discursive mediations, and symbolic disputes in specific contexts of production and reception. Based on this understanding, the methodology adopted is anchored in the iconographic and iconological analysis of images produced about the war against Paraguay, especially those published in the 19th-century illustrated press, notably by Henrique Fleiuss and Angelo Agostini, and in the collection *Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War*. These images are approached as visual constructions that integrate regimes of representation, memory, and identity, in a field strained by aesthetic, political, and market interests.

The iconographic analysis developed in this work is based on the methodological assumptions of Erwin Panofsky, particularly his proposal of a pre-iconographic, iconographic, and iconological approach. The first level, descriptive in nature, aims to identify the formal elements of the composition—figures, gestures, settings, objects—taking into account the materiality of the image, its framing, and its visual codes. The second level, interpretative in nature, seeks to recognize the themes, motifs, and narratives represented, connecting them to a cultural and symbolic repertoire shared by the audiences of the time. Finally, the third level, iconological, proposes a deeper interpretation of the image, linked to the values, ideological structures, and worldviews that organize its production and enjoyment.

This interpretative approach, however, is approached with attention to the specificities of the context of nineteenth-century visual culture. Working with press images and official lithographs requires a keen eye on the technical, editorial, and commercial conditions that shaped the production and circulation of these representations.

In the case of Fleiuss and Agostini's engravings, the images are analyzed in their insertion within illustrated periodicals, taking into account their location on the page, their relationship with the editorial texts, and the communication strategies with the readers. In the case of the *Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War*, the focus is on the iconographic project as a whole, investigating the criteria for selecting the represented episodes, the visual language adopted, the pedagogical and patriotic meanings attributed to the collection, and its forms of circulation.

Furthermore, the methodology adopted is informed by contemporary debates on visual culture, particularly regarding the approach to images as forms of knowledge and as devices of power. Inspired by authors such as WJT Mitchell, Georges Didi-Huberman, and Peter Burke, this research considers that images not only reflect reality but actively participate in its constitution, operating as historical statements that articulate affects, narratives, and symbolic disputes. In this sense, images of war are not treated as mere illustrations of events, but as forms of meaning production that interfere with collective memory, processes of subjectivation, and the elaboration of social and national identities.

From an operational standpoint, the analysis of the images is carried out based on a documentary corpus that includes, on the one hand, engravings produced by Fleiuss and Agostini between 1864 and 1870, published in periodicals such as *Semana Illustrada* and *A Vida Fluminense*, and, on the other hand, the lithographs from the collection *Historical Pictures of the Paraguayan War*. The selection of images took into account criteria such as: 1) prominence in the visual imaginary of the war; 2) thematic and compositional diversity; 3)

presence in spaces of public circulation and enjoyment (newspapers, schools, government offices); and 4) historical and symbolic relevance in the process of constructing the memory of the conflict.

Each selected image is examined in conjunction with its production context, which includes data about the artist, the publication medium, the specific historical moment in which it was produced, and the discourses that permeate it. The analysis takes into account the compositional elements of the scene, the characters represented, the background settings, body language, gestures, iconographic codes, and the effects of framing, light, and shadow. The use of symbols and allegories, such as flags, weapons, horses, or allegories of the homeland, which contribute to the construction of a shared visual lexicon, is also observed.

Based on this method, the research seeks to understand how the image operates as a pedagogical and ideological device, offering a guided reading of facts and contributing to the construction of legitimizing historical narratives. In this process, the tensions between visibility and silencing are privileged: what is emphasized, what is omitted, who appears in a prominent position and who remains on the margins. The image is thus treated as a field of political dispute, capable of highlighting the social and symbolic conflicts of the period.

Regarding the illustrated press, the newspapers analyzed are considered cultural artifacts that interact with the demands of the publishing market, the political strategies of the editors, and the expectations of the reading public. The study examines the newspapers in their entirety, observing not only the images but also the editorial texts, chronicles, battle reports, poems, and advertisements, composing a broader picture of the graphic culture of the period. This allows us to capture the intertextuality between visual and verbal languages and understand how they articulate to construct meanings about the war.

Historical Paintings collection, a more institutionalized approach to visual memory is adopted. Here, the focus is on the production, editing, and distribution policies of the collection, based on primary sources such as ministerial reports, acquisition records, and distribution lists for schools and public offices. The analysis of these sources allows us to understand the pedagogical uses of the images, the official objectives of consolidating the heroic memory of the conflict, and the ways in which the State used art to shape the national imagination.

The methodology also includes dialogue with secondary sources such as articles, theses, dissertations, and exhibition catalogs, which address the iconography of the war, the artists involved, the illustrated press, and the memory policies of the Empire. These references are critically mobilized in order to enrich the reading of the images and situate them within broader historiographical and theoretical debates. The reception of the images at different historical

moments is also considered, problematizing the ways in which they were appropriated, forgotten, or re-actualized over time.

Finally, it is worth highlighting that the research is structured from an interdisciplinary perspective, crossing knowledge from History, Art, Communication, and Visual Anthropology. This intersection allows for a richer and more complex approach to images, recognizing in them both their aesthetic dimension and their social function. Instead of seeking a univocal reading, the methodology adopted values the ambiguity, polysemy, and instability of the meanings produced by visual representations, understanding that they are always traversed by disputes and plural interpretations.

In summary, the methodology used in this research combines rigorous iconographic analysis, a critical reading of the historical context, and attention to the editorial, institutional, and pedagogical devices that shaped the circulation of images. The image is understood here as a dense document, where discourses, affects, memories, and power are condensed. It is within this horizon that the analysis of visual representations of the war against Paraguay is inscribed, with the commitment to contribute to a critical history of visibility and memory in nineteenth-century Brazil.

VISUAL CULTURE

The war against Paraguay, across its multiple fronts—diplomatic, military, economic, and symbolic—also revealed itself as fertile ground for the flourishing of a visual culture regime that was consolidating in 19th-century Brazil. Visual expression, in this context, was not a mere adornment to the historical narrative, but a constitutive form of meaning-making and mediation of war experiences. Engravings, lithographs, caricatures, portraits, allegories, and maps comprised a visual repertoire that informed, educated, moved, and disciplined. The illustrated press and iconographic projects such as the collection * *Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War* * exemplify this process, each in its own way, highlighting the role of the image in the construction of the national imaginary and in the struggle for memories of the conflict.

The concept of visual culture, as formulated by authors such as Nicholas Mirzoeff (2003) and Peter Burke (2004), implies recognizing the centrality of images in social life, as well as the ways in which they are produced, consumed, and interpreted in different historical contexts. More than iconographic supports, images integrate systems of signification that involve material practices, reproduction technologies, regimes of visibility, affects, and political disputes. Thus, understanding the war against Paraguay as a visual phenomenon is also

to understand the ways in which the gaze was trained, guided, and disciplined by institutions, publishers, schools, and apparatuses of the imperial state.

In the case of the illustrated press, this visual culture manifests itself through the combination of graphic language and journalistic discourse, composing an aesthetic characteristic of nineteenth-century modernity. Newspapers not only reported events from the *front*, but also carried a certain degree of visual dramatization. The vigorous lines of Angelo Agostini and the more conventional compositions of Henrique Fleiuss offered the public scenes of the war that oscillated between patriotic exaltation and criticism, whether veiled or explicit, of the imperial project.

The reader of that time did not consume these images passively: they read, interpreted, reacted, and debated them. Some of these images were displayed in the windows of printing houses, discussed in cafes and salons, cut out and collected. Printed visibility, in this sense, integrated a circuit of cultural practices that articulated the sensitive with the political. As WJT Mitchell (2005) reminds us, images are "living beings" that act in the world, that interpellate the viewer, that produce effects. There is, therefore, no neutrality in the image: every representation is also a taking of a position.

The visual culture of war was also manifested through the mobilization of established iconographic genres, such as historical painting, adapted to the graphic format and the publishing circuit. In the pages of periodicals, battle scenes, portraits of commanders, panoramas of fortresses, and allegorical representations of the nation composed a mosaic that informed the public and simultaneously educated them visually. Artists selected angles, emphasized heroes, attenuated or highlighted certain discomforts, depending on their ideological position. In this process, war became image and, as image, became memory.

It is important to highlight that the visual culture of war operated according to different regimes of visibility, which often clashed. On one hand, there was the monumentalizing visibility of official projects, which sought to establish the war as a national epic. The collection "*Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War*" is a clear example of this trend: its lithographs, inspired almost entirely by academic paintings or sketches, present the war as a field of honor, glory, and noble sacrifice. The fallen bodies appear composed, the soldiers form harmonious ranks, the generals point proudly towards the horizon. Violence is aesthetic, suffering is discipline, chaos is erased in the name of visual order.

On the other hand, there was also the critical, satirical, and fragmented visibility of the illustrated press, especially in the hands of Agostini. His caricatures explored the grotesque, the disproportionate, the blatant. They showed the despair of the soldiers, the suffering of the

civilians, the hypocrisy of the elites. Instead of compositional harmony, what was seen was bewilderment, exaggeration, confrontation. This aesthetic of dissent, while entertaining, also deconstructed official discourses, offering other possibilities of seeing and, therefore, of thinking about the war.

Between these two poles lay zones of ambivalence and negotiation. Henrique Fleiuss, for example, moved between factual illustration and allegorical representation, producing images that, while aligned with imperial discourse, also revealed fissures, ambiguities, and tensions. In some engravings, the glory of the Empire shares space with the suffering of soldiers, military discipline with the improvisation of the battlefield. This ambivalence is characteristic of a visual culture that, far from being homogeneous, was traversed by multiple interests, sensibilities, and voices.

Another important aspect of the visual culture of war was its pedagogical instrumentalization. Images not only informed, they taught. In schools, the *Historical Pictures collection* was used as an award or ornament, given to outstanding students or decorating classrooms, serving as a basis for lessons in civic morality. The visual imagery of war, in this case, was mobilized as a strategy for national formation, shaping the gaze of new generations towards a specific reading of the past: the reading of heroic sacrifice, national unity, and imperial legitimacy. The image, here, fulfilled its disciplinary function.

This pedagogical use of images was not neutral. It was linked to a state-promoted policy of memory, interested in consolidating a single narrative about the conflict. By privileging certain scenes and silencing others, by highlighting certain characters and omitting others, this visual culture contributed to the construction of a selective memory of the war, in which the presence of Black people, Indigenous people, women, and enlisted soldiers was extremely reduced or, in rare cases, aestheticized. The war was narrated and shown to viewers as a feat solely and exclusively of the elites.

However, it is important to note that even these normative images were not immune to reappropriations, deviant readings, and unforeseen uses. Visual culture is, by definition, a field of tensions. As Georges Didi-Huberman (2010) points out, the image never fully closes itself off in one meaning: it escapes, resists, shifts. The iconography of war, however controlled it may have been, was also a space of ambiguity, of openness to the gaze of the other, of fissures in the monument. And it is in this space of fissure that the historian of visibility must operate, seeking the signs of dissent, the gaps in representation, the interrupted gestures.

Therefore, understanding the visual culture of the war against Paraguay also means recognizing its silences and absences. What was not shown? Who was not represented? What

scenes were systematically avoided? Official images avoid depicting the devastation of Paraguayan cities, the piled-up corpses, the starving bodies, the sexual violence. The iconography of suffering, when it exists, is always mediated by a compassionate and disciplining gaze. There is no room for screams, despair, or insubordination. The image produced is one of heroism, the nobility of pain, the discipline of death.

By juxtaposing these images with period accounts, letters, diaries, and testimonies, the research reveals the distance between the represented visuality and the lived experience. Visual culture, in this sense, is not a reflection of reality, but its symbolic operation. It selects, organizes, and aestheticizes. And, in doing so, it constructs memories, silences dissent, and legitimizes power.

In short, the war against Paraguay was also a war of images – both ideologically and commercially. It was fought not only with swords and cannons, but also with pencils, burins, and printing presses. The visual culture that emerged from it was a battleground where political projects, social sensibilities, and regimes of memory clashed. The analysis of this visual culture, as proposed by both studies presented here, allows us to understand the power of images in the constitution of the national imaginary, and invites us to look critically at the ways in which we see and remember past conflicts.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The investigation of visual representations of the war against Paraguay, anchored in the analysis of the works of Henrique Fleiuss and Angelo Agostini and in the collection *Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War*, highlighted the centrality of the image in the construction of the social, political, and affective memories of this conflict. Throughout the research, it was demonstrated that the war was not restricted to the battlefield, nor was it limited to the pages of military reports and imperial decrees: it was also a war of representations. And these representations, produced, consumed, and contested within a visual culture in formation, played an active role in shaping the nineteenth-century national imaginary.

Among the various media available in 19th-century Brazil, the illustrated press emerged as a privileged space for the visual enunciation of war. Through the pages of periodicals such as *Semana Illustrada* and *A Vida Fluminense*, artists/editors like Fleiuss and Agostini built an iconographic repertoire that not only informed readers but also summoned them to symbolic participation in the war effort. The reader thus became a spectator of battles, a judge of strategies, an accomplice to victories, and a witness to suffering. Through engravings, war

entered homes, squares, and social circles, transforming itself into a visual spectacle and an instrument of ideological mobilization.

However, as demonstrated throughout the analysis, this process did not occur in a linear or univocal way. The visuality of war was, from its origin, a field of tensions and disputes. Images that exalted the bravery of the imperial soldier coexisted with those that satirized the logistical delays of the troops; heroic portraits of generals were challenged by caricatures that exposed the contradictions of the official discourse. Amidst censorship, pressure from the publishing market, and the expectations of the reading public, illustrators operated with an ambivalent repertoire, often blurring the lines between criticism and consecration, denunciation and adherence. The illustrated press, far from being merely a transmission belt for imperial propaganda, was also a space of ambiguity and, at times, resistance.

This ambiguity is also manifested in the different regimes of visuality mobilized by editorial and institutional projects. The collection **Historical Paintings of the Paraguayan War**, in turn, represents the most systematic effort to monumentalize the visual memory of the conflict. Supported by the State, conceived for circulation in schools and public offices, the collection crystallizes an official narrative of the war: the selected episodes, the portrayed heroes, the represented enemies and, above all, the imposed silences reveal a visual pedagogy that seeks to discipline the gaze and fix an epic and civilizing version of the campaign. The academic aesthetic, the ordered composition of the scenes and the idealization of bodies and gestures reinforce this indoctrinating function of the images.

When comparing these representations with other sources and recent historiographical studies, it becomes clear that the iconography of war, at the time, served the function of organizing the affections and meanings of the war experience. It helped to make visible what was intended to be remembered—and to erase what was desired to be forgotten. Significant absences marked this production: little is seen, for example, of the civil devastation in Paraguay, of the participation of freed blacks in combat, of sexual violence against women, of the precariousness of field hospitals. The image selected and hierarchized pain, aestheticizing horror and inscribing violence within the limits of what is representable.

Therefore, this research is also part of a critical proposal for reading images: not only as iconographic sources, but as fields of force, as spaces of enunciation and silencing, as technologies of power and devices of memory. By adopting an approach inspired by Panofskian iconology, but traversed by the contributions of visual culture and the history of sensibilities, the work sought to highlight that every image carries, at the same time, the visible and the invisible, the said and the forbidden. Understanding the visual culture of war is, therefore,

understanding the ways in which 19th-century Brazil saw itself—and, in doing so, traced the contours of its national identity amidst blood, glory, and printed paper.

The prominent presence of figures like Henrique Fleiuss and Angelo Agostini in this process illustrates the role of artists as mediators between the field of power, the publishing market, and the reading public. Fleiuss, more aligned with the imperial project, offered images that exalted the achievements of the Army, portraying war as an expression of order and progress. Agostini, in turn, explored caricature as a form of social criticism, exposing the contradictions of the Empire and expanding the limits of laughter as a political language. Both, albeit through different paths, actively participated in the symbolic dispute surrounding the war, contributing to forging the contours of a visual memory still present today in archives, books, and historiography.

By recognizing the image as a historical agent and an essential source, this research reinforces the need to include visibility in debates about memory, identity, and power. It is not about subjecting the image to the text, as often happens in the historiographical tradition, but about listening to it in its own language, with its own strategies of enunciation. The war against Paraguay, as analyzed here, was not only the object of the image: it was also constructed by it. The engravings not only document the war; they constitute it as a symbolic event, as a historical fact, and as a cultural heritage.

Nineteenth-century visual culture, with its illustrated newspapers, lithographic collections, and commemorative albums, established a regime of visibility that remains operative in contemporary ways of narrating the past. Many images of the war continue to be reproduced in textbooks, documentaries, and exhibitions, sometimes without proper critical contextualization. The act of revisiting, interpreting, and problematizing them is, therefore, also an act of historiographical responsibility, aimed at breaking with the automatism of memory and opening space for more complex and plural readings of the conflict.

In this sense, the present research does not intend to end the debate, but to contribute to the expansion of the field of investigation on the iconography of the war against Paraguay. The visual culture of the conflict, as demonstrated, offers multiple analytical possibilities: from the analysis of graphic materialities to the study of the affects mobilized by the images, passing through the narrative strategies of the artists and the pedagogical uses of the engravings. Visibility, as a language and as a social practice, reveals itself as fertile ground for understanding the past and, with it, also the present of our disputes over memory and identity.

Finally, it is worth highlighting that the developments of this research point to new avenues of investigation. Among them, the study of contemporary receptions of these images

in the fields of historical education, museology, and exhibitions about war stands out. How do 19th-century images circulate today? What interpretations do they provoke? What silences do they still reproduce?

In summary, this research reinforces the place of the image as a legitimate and complex object of historical research, capable of illuminating shadowy areas, deconstructing myths, and reconstructing the meanings of lived experience. The war was depicted; and it is through this depiction, this persistent trace in time, that we continue to be called upon to interpret it, to question it, and to reread its meanings in the history of Brazil.

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